

THE CONCEPT OF A NOMINATIVE CHAIN AND NOMINAL
REPETITIONS

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The thesis discusses the concept of nomination from various interpretation approaches starting with a nominative chain to nominal repetition.

Each phenomenon in the language is assigned a specific, unique name. This is where the theory of nomination comes from - the naming process in which the elements of language fully (or partially) reflect the designated objects. E.S. Kubryakov characterizes the act of nomination as a speech-thought process aimed either at choosing a ready-made designation existing in the language for the named phenomenon and thoughts about this phenomenon, or at creating a suitable name for it.

Nevertheless N.D. Tamarchenko interprets the concept of nomination in a narrow sense, not including qualities, attitudes, and actions in the substantive aspect of the nomination. In most cases, she explores nomination through literary texts. So N.D. Tamarchenko interprets the concept of nomination in a narrow sense, not including qualities, attitudes, and actions in the substantive aspect of the nomination. Repeated nominations in the text have become the subject of consideration by many linguists [2]. In the works of German researchers, terms such as Substitution (substitution), and *Wiederaufnahme* (renewal) are used to denote this concept. The famous German linguist K. Brinker addresses the phenomenon of repeated nomination. According to him, on the same referential attribution of words or phrases in the text. The same referential reference (Referenzidentität), or coreference (Koreferenz) means that the nomination used refers to the same object of extra-linguistic reality to which the previous nomination belonged. Such an object of extra-linguistic reality can be a person, an

object, a situation, an event, an action, a representation, etc. The scientist says that the name of an already named object can either be repeated, or replaced by another noun or substantive group, or replaced by a pronoun and gives relevant examples. He notes that nouns may not be complete synonyms or be in a relationship of contextual synonymy (that is, not be synonyms at all out of context). Hence, he gives the example of a pair of nouns Auto (car) and Fahrzeug (vehicle), where Fahrzeug is broader in meaning, that is, it is a hypernym; also in one of the texts he cited as an example, nouns that have different meanings but refer to the same person are used as repeated nominations: Mann (man), Facharbeiter (specialist), Betrunkenener (drunk), Gefangener (prisoner).

M. Averintseva identifies cases when a complete repetition of a word or expression is made and when only one of its semantic parts is repeated. In the second case, the connection between repeated words can be either word-formative (Vogel (bird) – Vögelchen (bird) – Vogelnest (bird's nest)) or purely semantic (Gold (gold) – Schatz (treasures)). Since we are talking about replacing one nomination with another, M. Averintseva-Klish calls this process Substitution. According to her, substitution is possible when words are in appropriate semantic relationships - synonymous, hyponymic-hyperonymic, metaphorical. The researcher also notes that for substitution, words must have the same or similar semes (so-called isotopes). Words with common semes form isotopic chains (Isotopie-Ketten) in the text.

It is necessary to pay attention to the concept of an isotopic chain used by M. Averintseva-Klish. This concept is closely related to the concept of a nominative chain. As in the case of nominative chains, isotopy is based on the phenomenon of "semantic equivalence," in other words, the components of the isotopic chain carry the same semes. Isotopic chains help form the structure of the text and are an indicator of its coherence. Its components, as a rule, form a thematic group. However, they are not always at the same time components of the nominative chain. Thus, in the example of M. Averintseva-Klish Vogel - Vögelchen -

Vogelnest, the components are united by a common seme, which means they form an isotopic chain, but designate different objects, that is, they have different referential references, and, therefore, are not components of a chain of repeated nominations [3].

T.M. Nikolaeva notes that, from all types of repetitions, nominal repetitions play a particularly important role. She also names some types of nominal repetitions: pure repetition, replacement with a synonym, pronoun, with a word of a broader/narrower meaning, with periphrases, antonym. It can be assumed that one of the most important functions of repeated nominations is that they allow the author to add information about the object. According to the fair statement of A.A. Gromykhina, “The combination of various nominations creates a “nominative” portrait of an object, which sets the semantic direction in the text.”

V.G. Gak emphasizes this feature of re-nomination. The scientist says that since repeated nomination names an object already named earlier. This allows you to vary the repeated nominations, using them to add an additional expressive touch to the emerging image. The scientist classifies repeated nominations as non-autonomous, that is, those that depend on other nominations. V.G. Gak identifies the following types of re-nomination:

1. According to the form of the nominee: identical (if the nominee receives the same concept) and variable (if the repeated nomination differs from the previous one);

2. From the point of view of the nominator: single-focused (if nominations are given by the same nominator) and multi-focused (if nominations are given by different nominators);

3. By location towards each other: distant (separated by other statements) and conjugate (following directly after each other).

4. According to the relative position of indirect and direct nomination: reprise (indirect designation follows the direct one) and anticipation (indirect designation precedes the direct one) [1].

The list of used literature

1. Гак В.Г. К типологии лингвистических номинаций. М., 1977. Р.234
2. Тamarченко Н.Д. Поэтика: словарь актуальных терминов и понятий. М., 2008. Р. 147
3. Brinker K. Linguistische Textanalyse. Berlin, 2010. Р. 26.

